

Addressing Nuclear Criticality Safety Training Needs

Walid A. Metwally,^{1,*} Steven Biegalski,² Pavel Tsvetkov,³ Alex Lang,¹ Douglas Bowen¹

¹Oak Ridge National Laboratory, 1 Bethel Valley Road, Oak Ridge, TN 37830, USA

²Georgia Institute of Technology, North Avenue NW Atlanta, GA 30332, USA

³Texas A&M University, 400 Bizzell Street, College Station, TX 77843, USA

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803616

ABSTRACT

Nuclear criticality safety ensures that nuclear materials remain subcritical across various applications, including facility operations, transportation, storage, and research. A new nuclear criticality safety training program has been developed to address critical knowledge gaps among emerging professionals in the nuclear industry. This program is funded by the US Department of Energy's Nuclear Criticality Safety Program and is developed by Oak Ridge National Laboratory, the Georgia Institute of Technology, and Texas A&M University. The program is a two-level certificate program that combines a comprehensive self-paced online course (Level I) with a practical 1-day hands-on training session (Level II). Level I consists of 25 modules that cover topics such as nuclear fundamentals, criticality calculations, safety analysis, and evaluation methodologies, and Level II provides practical experience in neutron shielding, moderation, and detector applications via real-world experiments. Since its launch in the summer of 2025, the program has attracted nearly 90 registrants, including both undergraduate/graduate students and employed professionals. A multichannel outreach strategy—including direct communications, digital platforms, and professional conferences—has contributed to this diverse participation. Thirty-two students have completed the Level I course, and 8 have completed Level II. Evaluations of assessment data and student feedback surveys are ongoing and will facilitate the continuous improvement of the program and enhance training effectiveness.

Keywords: nuclear criticality safety (NCS), online training, hands-on training, US Department of Energy (DOE) Nuclear Criticality Safety Program (NCSP)

* metwallywa@ornl.gov

Notice: This manuscript has been authored by UT-Battelle, LLC, under contract DE-AC05-00OR22725 with the US Department of Energy (DOE). The US government retains and the publisher, by accepting the article for publication, acknowledges that the US government retains a nonexclusive, paid-up, irrevocable, worldwide license to publish or reproduce the published form of this manuscript, or allow others to do so, for US government purposes. DOE will provide public access to these results of federally sponsored research in accordance with the DOE Public Access Plan (<http://energy.gov/downloads/doe-public-access-plan>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear criticality safety (NCS), an essential discipline in the nuclear industry, ensures that nuclear materials in different configurations always maintain subcritical conditions. The application of NCS is found in different areas, including facility operations, transportation, storage, and research. Facility operations involve the front-end life cycle of nuclear fuel—from mining, enrichment, and fabrication to its use in reactors or nonreactor programs—and transportation manages the secure movement of the nuclear material at various stages in its entire life cycle. The storage of nuclear fuel encompasses new fuel vaults, spent fuel pools, dry casks, independent storage installations, and permanent disposal. Research and critical experiments are normally conducted at universities and national laboratories.

Training is required for NCS professionals and is prescribed in several international [1,2] and US domestic [3–5] guidance documents. In addition to the training performed for new professionals in national laboratories, some of the US efforts to train NCS professionals include the following:

- 1) US Department of Energy (DOE) Nuclear Criticality Safety Program (NCSP) [6]: NCSP offers two courses to address training requirements. The first course is a 1-week course for managers and criticality safety officers; this course is intended for professionals responsible for criticality safety. The second course is a 2-week criticality safety engineer course designed to train and educate new personnel entering the criticality safety field.
- 2) Safety Analysis Review for Packaging (SARP) Analyst Course [7]: The SARP analyst course equips personnel specializing in radiation shielding and NCS with the skills needed to prepare and review SARP documents related to the packaging and transportation of fissionable materials.
- 3) Nuclear Criticality Safety Pipeline Courses:
 - a. Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) and Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) collaborate with the University of California, Berkeley to offer a semester-long course on NCS. This course covers the fundamentals of criticality safety, familiarizes students with national and consensus standards, and trains them in preparing criticality safety evaluations [8].
 - b. LANL collaborates with the University of New Mexico to offer an online course that provides a comprehensive introduction on NCS. LANL criticality safety staff mentor student groups for a process analysis project and criticality safety evaluation project [9].
 - c. Savannah River Nuclear Solutions (SRNS) recently collaborated with North Carolina State University to develop and deliver a course to support the growing need for specialists in NCS engineering [10].

A new NCS pipeline training program has been developed by Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), the Georgia Institute of Technology, and Texas A&M University [11]. This program is a university-based NCS training certificate program supported by DOE NCSP [12]. The program objectives are as follows:

- a) To address knowledge gaps among new NCS professionals,
- b) To enhance student preparation for the 2-week NCSP training course,
- c) To sustain the pipeline of qualified nuclear criticality specialists for the DOE laboratory complex, and, ultimately,
- d) To reduce the attrition of NCS professionals.

The program is designed for undergraduate and graduate engineering, physics, and mathematics students, with no prerequisite for NCS.

2. PROGRAM STRUCTURE

The NCS training program is structured into two levels. The Level I course is a series of self-paced online lectures, videos, and exercises that cover a wide range of subjects, including nuclear fundamentals, nuclear criticality, k_{eff} calculation, safety limits, criticality safety accidents, validation approaches and methods, and documentation. The material for this certificate was developed by the Georgia Institute of Technology, Texas A&M University, and ORNL. Upon successful completion of the Level I course, students receive a certificate and are allowed to register for the Level II course.

2.1. Level I

Excluding the introduction and summary, the Level I certificate course is composed of 25 modules that cover the different aspects of NCS. The full list of modules is as follows:

1. Course Introduction and Nuclear Criticality Safety Overview
2. Nuclear Particles and Nuclear Notation
3. Nuclear Structure and Radioactive Decay
4. Atom Density, Cross Sections, and Nuclear Data
5. Radiation Interaction with Matter and Reaction Rates
6. Criticality and 6-Factor Formula
7. Neutron Flux and Fick's Law
8. Diffusion Equation
9. Critical Condition from Diffusion Equation
10. Delayed Neutrons and Pulses
11. Factors in Criticality Safety and MAGICMERV
12. Criticality Safety Considerations for U and Pu Systems
13. Hand Calculations
14. History and Lessons Learned of Process Criticality Accidents
15. Safety Culture and Formality of Operations
16. Process Analysis (Part 1)
17. Process Analysis (Part 2)
18. Calculation/Assessment Lecture
19. Control Implementation
20. Alarms and Emergency Response
21. Validation Requirements from ANS-8.1 and ANS-8.24
22. Validation Approaches and Methods
23. Examples of Use in Validation and Control Selection
24. Criticality Safety Evaluation Process
25. Criticality Safety Evaluations Writing and Steps
26. Criticality Safety Evaluations for U and Pu Systems
27. Summary and Review

There is a quiz at the end of each module. The students interact with the Level I course content through the ORNL Learning Management System, gAxis.

2.2. Level II

The Level II course is a 1-day practical session that covers key aspects of NCS. It focuses on important topics such as neutron shielding, neutron moderation, and controls for approaching criticality—illustrated through a 1/M subcritical measurement experiment. Additionally, participants conduct gamma radiation measurements to enhance their knowledge of detectors and shielding. To date, the Level II hands-on sessions have been held at the Georgia Institute of Technology.

3. PROGRESS AND CURRENT STATUS

All the course materials for Level I and Level II have been developed and are currently being utilized. Registration for the Level I course began in the summer of 2025, and nearly 90 students have enrolled to date. Of these students, 32 completed the Level I course and started registering for the Level II course.

The first offering of the Level II course was at the Georgia Institute of Technology in October 2025, and eight students have completed it so far. Figure 1 shows the student distribution across both levels.

Figure 1. Distribution of students in the Level I and Level II courses.

Although the program has mainly targeted undergraduate and graduate students, a number of employed professionals registered for the course to broaden their skillsets. These registrants view the course as a continuing education opportunity to enhance their current knowledge base or transition into a new career field. Figure 2 shows the status of registered students.

Figure 2. Professional status of registered students in the course.

The course was promoted using several communication channels. Direct emails were sent to engineering departments, and information was featured on NCSP, DOE, and ORNL websites as well as on ORNL’s social media platforms. Additionally, a couple papers were presented at American Nuclear Society (ANS) conferences. Over time, some students learned about the course through colleague referrals and by conducting routine web searches. This outreach strategy helped broaden the course’s visibility and attract a diverse group of participants. Figure 3 provides more details on how students learned about the program.

Figure 3: Sources of student knowledge about the program.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A new NCS training program has been successfully established to address knowledge gaps among emerging NCS professionals and sustain a pipeline of qualified staff in this field. The comprehensive two-level structure of the course combines a self-paced online coursework portion and a practical 1-day hands-on training session. The enrollment data indicate strong engagement and successful launch of the program, with nearly 90 students enrolled in the Level I course and a growing number transitioning to Level II and completing the program.

Attraction to the program extended beyond the primary target groups of undergraduate and graduate students to employed professionals seeking continuing education opportunities or a career transition. This diversity in participation highlights the program’s effectiveness in responding to growing needs in NCS. The multichannel outreach approach—including direct communication, online platforms, and professional conferences—has successfully engaged a wide and diverse audience.

Moving forward, considerable effort will be devoted to evaluating the course assessment results and analyzing student feedback surveys. This analysis will be used to identify areas for ongoing course improvement. Additionally, we plan to survey students completing the Level II course in the near future to gain insights into their chosen career paths.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the NCSP, which is funded and managed by the National Nuclear Security Administration for DOE.

REFERENCES

- [1] International Atomic Energy Agency. "Nuclear Security Recommendations on Physical Protection of Nuclear Material and Nuclear Facilities." INFCIRC/225/Revision 5 (2011). URL: https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1481_web.pdf.
- [2] International Organization for Standardization. "Nuclear Criticality Safety – Nuclear Criticality Safety Training for Operations." ISO 23133:2021 (2021). URL: <https://www.iso.org/standard/74671.html>.
- [3] US Nuclear Regulatory Commission. "Title 10, Code of Federal Regulations, Part 73.25: Performance Capabilities for Physical Protection of Strategic Special Nuclear Material in Transit." URL: <https://www.nrc.gov/reading-rm/doc-collections/cfr/part073/full-text.html#part073-0025>.
- [4] American Nuclear Society. "ANSI/ANS-8.20-2025: Nuclear Criticality Safety Training for Fissionable Material Operations Outside Reactors." American Nuclear Society (2025).
- [5] American Nuclear Society. "ANSI/ANS-8.26-2024: Nuclear Criticality Safety Engineer Training and Qualification Program." American Nuclear Society (2024).
- [6] US Department of Energy Nuclear Criticality Safety Program. "Focus Area: Training and Education." Accessed October 3, 2025. URL: <https://ncsp.llnl.gov/training-education>.
- [7] W. A. Metwally, R. Bean, and B. Loftin. "Oak Ridge National Laboratory's Role in the US Department of Energy's Packaging Certification Program." In *Proceedings of the 21st International Symposium on the Packaging and Transportation of Radioactive Materials*, Institute of Nuclear Materials Management, San Antonio, Texas, USA (2025).
- [8] S. E. Coleman, A. J. Yamanaka, and W. J. Zywiec. "Criticality Safety Evaluation Project Development for University of California Berkeley Nuclear Criticality Safety Pipeline Course." In *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Nuclear Criticality Safety*, Sendai, Japan (2023).
- [9] C. M. Perfetti. "The University of New Mexico's online nuclear criticality safety course material." In *Proceedings of the Nuclear Criticality Safety Division Topical Meeting (NCSD 2022)*, Anaheim, California (2022).
- [10] American Nuclear Society. "NC State & SRNS partner to attract young talent." Accessed October 3, 2025. URL: <https://www.ans.org/news/2025-05-27/article-7069/nc-state-srns-partner-to-attract-young-talent/>.
- [11] Oak Ridge National Laboratory. "NC Course 2025." Accessed October 3, 2025. URL: <https://events.ornl.gov/ncscourse2025/>.
- [12] National Criticality Safety Program (NCSP). (2025) "NCSP five-year execution plan FY2026–2030." Accessed October 3, 2025. Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (2025). URL: <https://ncsp.llnl.gov/program-management/ncsp-five-year-execution-plan>.